

COMPARISON OF TWO CITIES:MIRROR TOWN PLANNING

¹Prathamesh Gurme, ²Sangram Patil

¹UG Scholar, ²Assistant Professor

Bharati Vidhyapeeth's College of Engineering,

Lavale, Pune.

India

ABSTRACT:

Town Planning is must for any structural point of view as it offers proper functioning and circulation. Urban planning is also referred to as urban and regional planning, regional planning, town planning, city planning, rural planning or some combination in various areas worldwide priority given for Town Planning plays vital role defining success of any city or town. So here is outlook and comparative analysis has been carried out on the basis of structural planning and survey of respective Places showing similar town planning originated from single point and goes in the way of radiated rays form i.e. in circular form.

Keywords: *Town Planning, Planning and control, Town Planning, Urban mobility solutions. Quality of life in cities.*

INTRODUCTION:

Town planning is the planning and design of all the new buildings, roads, and parks in a place in order to make them attractive and convenient for the people who live there Urban planning is a technical and political process concerned with the development and use of land, planning permission, protection and use of the environment, public welfare, and the design of the urban environment, including air, water, and the infrastructure passing into and out of urban areas. There is analysis taken for the two cities showing structurally same town Planning in same manner these two places are modified so this gives brief analytic comparison between the city of Paris near the Arc De Triomphe monument of France and Ganj Golai of Latur city from state of Maharashtra in India. so here is survey shows that how these inter related with each with somehow similar Town Planning and mentioning the planning of Paris was created earlier than Latur's Ganj Golai.

ARC DE TRIOMPHE,PARIS [FRANCE]

The Arc de Triomphe de l'Étoile (French pronunciation: [aʁk də tʁijɔ̃f də letwal], Triumphal Arch of the Star) is one of the most famous monuments in Paris, standing at the western end of the Champs-Élysées at the center of Place Charles de Gaulle, formerly named Place de l'Étoile — the étoile or "star" of the juncture formed by its twelve radiating avenues.

Figure No 01: ARC DE TRIOMPHE, PARIS [FRANCE]

The Arc de Triomphe should not be confused with a smaller arch, the Arc de Triomphe du Carrousel, which stands west of the Louvre. The Arc de Triomphe honours those who fought and died for France in the French Revolutionary and Napoleonic Wars, with the names of all French victories and generals inscribed on its inner and outer surfaces. Beneath its vault lies the Tomb of the Unknown Soldier from World War I.

As the central cohesive element of the Axe historique (historic axis, a sequence of monuments and grand thoroughfares on a route running from the courtyard of the Louvre to the Grande Arche de la Défense), the Arc de Triomphe was designed by Jean Chalgrin in 1806, and its iconographic program pits heroically nude French youths against bearded Germanic warriors in chain mail. It set the tone for public monuments with triumphant patriotic messages.

ALTERNATIVE NAMES: ARC DE TRIOMPHE DE L'ÉTOILE

GENERAL INFORMATION

Type	: Triumphal Arch	Height	: 50 m (164 ft)
Architectural style	: Neoclassicism	Wide	: 45 m (148 ft)
Location	: Place Charles de Gaulle (formerly Place de l'Étoile)	Deep	: 22 m (72 ft)
Coordinates	: 48.8738°N 2.2950°E	Design and construction	
Construction started	: 15 August 1806	Architect	: Jean Chalgrin, Louis-Etienne Héricart de Thury
Inaugurated	: 29 July 1836		

The Arc is located on the right bank of the Seine at the centre of a dodecagonal configuration of twelve radiating avenues. It was commissioned in 1806 after the victory at Austerlitz by Emperor Napoleon at the peak of his fortunes. Laying the foundations alone took two years and, in 1810, when Napoleon entered Paris from the west with his bride Archduchess Marie-Louise of Austria, he had a wooden mock-up of the completed arch constructed. The architect, Jean Chalgrin, died in 1811 and the work was taken over by Jean-Nicolas Huyot. During the Bourbon Restoration, construction was halted and it would not be completed until the reign of King Louis-Philippe, between 1833 and 1836, by the architects Goust, then Huyot, under the direction of Héricart de Thury. On 15 December 1840, brought back to France from Saint Helena, Napoleon's remains passed under it on their way to the Emperor's final resting place at the Invalides.[6] Prior to burial in the Pantheon, the body of Victor Hugo was displayed under the Arc during the night of 22 May 1885.

The sword carried by the Republic in the Marseillaise relief broke off on the day, it is said, that the Battle of Verdun began in 1916. The relief was immediately hidden by tarpaulins to conceal the accident and avoid any undesired ominous interpretation.

The Arc de Triomphe, located at the Place Charles de Gaulle commemorates Emperor Napoleon's victories. The arch was completed in 1836, long after Napoleon's reign had come to an end in the middle of the Place Charles de Gaulle, at the border of the 8th, 16th and 17th arrondissement stands one of the greatest arches in history: the Arc de Triomphe (arch of triumph)

The arch was commissioned by Napoleon in 1806 to commemorate his victories, but he was ousted before the arch was completed. In fact, it wasn't completed until 1836 during the reign of Louis-Philippe. The Arc de Triomphe is engraved with names of generals who commanded French troops during Napoleon's regime.

DESIGN

The design of the arch by Jean Chalgrin is based on the Arch of Titus in Rome. The Arc de Triomphe is much higher (50m versus 15m), but it has exactly the same proportions.

The triumphal arch is adorned with many reliefs, most of them commemorating the emperor's battles. Among them are the battle of Aboukir, Napoleon's victory over the Turkish and the Battle of Austerlitz, where Napoleon defeated the Austrians.

The best known relief is the Departure of the Volunteers in 1792, also known as the Marseillaise. At the top of the arch are thirty shields, each of them bears the name of one of Napoleon's successful battles. Below the arch is the Grave of the Unknown Soldiers, honoring the many who died during the First World War.

Figure No 02 : ARC DE TRIOMPHE, PARIS [FRANCE]

GANJ GOLAI, LATUR, MAHARASHTRA [INDIA]

Latur city has the famous 'Ganjgolai' as the central place of the city. The town planner Shri Faiyajuddin prepared the plan for the 'Ganjgolai Chowk'. The main building of the Golai is a huge two-storied structure which was constructed around the year 1917. In the middle of the circular structure is the temple of Goddess Ambabai. There are 16 roads connecting to this Golai and along these roads are separate markets selling all kinds of traditional local wares such as gold ornaments to footwear and food items from chilli to jaggery. Thus, the 'Ganjgolai' has become the main commercial and trade centre of this city.

Location: Maharashtra, India

Coordinates: 18.40°N 76.56°E

Country: India

State : Maharashtra

Figure No 03: GANJ GOLAI, LATUR, MAHARASHTRA [INDIA]

Latur has an ancient history, which probably dates to the Rashtrakuta period. It was home to a branch of Rashtrakutas which ruled the Deccan from 753 to 973 AD. The first Rashtrakuta king, Dantidurga, was from Lattalur , probably the ancient name for Latur. Ratnapur is also mentioned as an historic name for Latur.

The King Amoghavarsha of Rashtrakutas developed the Latur city, originally the native place of the Rashtrakutas. The Rashtrakutas who succeeded the Chalukyas of Badami in 753 AD called themselves the residents of Lattalur. It was, over the centuries, variously ruled by the Satavahanas, the Sakas, the Chalukyas, the Yadavas of Deogiri, the Delhi Sultans, the Bahamani rulers of South India, Adilshahi, and the Mughals.

Later in the 19th century, Latur became part of the independent princely state of Hyderabad. In 1905 it was merged with surrounding areas and renamed Latur tehsil, becoming part of Osmanabad district. Before 1948, Latur was a part of Hyderabad State under Nizam. The chief of Nizam's Razakar army, Qasim Rizwi, was from Latur.

After Indian independence and the merger of Hyderabad with the Indian Union, Osmanabad became part of Bombay Province. In 1960, with the creation of Maharashtra, Latur became one of its districts. On August 16, 1982, a separate Latur district was carved out of Osmanabad district. Ganj Golai is a famous round shaped building located in the heart of city Latur of Maharashtra, India. The sphere building is connected to the city through 16 roads. The double storied Ganj Golai was constructed in 1917.

Figure No 04: Layouts and Location Map (GANJ GOLAI, LATUR, MAHARASHTRA [INDIA])

It is host to the temple of Goddess Jagdamba. The center of building where temple is, was built again and a new 8 ft idol was established in 1989. The place has become a major commercial and trade center of Latur because along those 16 roads originating from Ganj Golai are separate markets selling all kind of things. The 16 roads are dedicated to each type of item like shoes, spices, jaggery, gold ornaments and other traditional items and are named after items like cloth line, metal line, saraf line, gift shop line etc.

Latur is a district town on the Solapur - Nanded route with rich historical importance. People visiting Latur definitely come to see this market and all the credit goes to Shri Faiyajuddin who designed the layout for Ganj golai.

INSPIRATION : GANJ GOLAI

- Ganj Golai is situated within the heart of the Latur city and is a two storey structure, which was built in 1917.
- The structure was planned by Shri Fayajuddin and it consists of a temple of Goddess Jagdamba located in the centre.
- Ganj Golai is connected with 16 roads with different markets that sell traditional items like gold ornaments, footwear and many more.
- This place is a well-known trade and commercial centre in the Latur city.

Figure No 05 : (GANJ GOLAI, LATUR, MAHARASHTRA [INDIA])

Recently based on this concept of circular planning another project is going to built in same city Latur to expand the market hub of Ganj Golai of Latur and it is inspired by this planning.

CONCLUSION:

Proposed type of town Planning made us very comfortable to live and circulation for better living in these cities and it proves that such kind of radial planning will be best to our living. More construction work should take place like these for betterment of planning of any town or city. Radial and Concentric driveways are pathways , segregating and at the same time connecting all spaces offerings easy vehicular and pedestrian movement.

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